

SMARTFIN CHAT

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ABSTRACT

Chat bots are intelligent systems that understand user's natural language queries and respond accordingly in a conversation, which is the focus of this study. It is more like a virtual assistant, people feel like they are talking with real person.

They speak the same language we do, can answer questions. In banks, at customer care centers and enquiry desks, human is insufficient and usually takes long time to process the single request which results in wastage of time and also reduce quality of customer service. The primary goal of this chat bot is, customer can interact with mentioning their queries in plain English and the chat bot can resolve their queries with appropriate response in return. The proposed system would help replicate the customer service experience with one difference that the customer would be interacting with a bot instead of a real person and yet get the queries attended and resolved.

It can extend daily life, by providing solutions to help desks, telephone answering systems, customer care centers. This paper explains the dataset that we have prepared from FAQs of banks websites, architecture and methodology used for developing such chat bot. Also this paper discusses the comparison of seven classification.

I INTRODUCTION

Banks play an important role in every country's economic development. In day-to-day life, everybody needs banks. But most of the people, especially the first-timers, struggle to know various procedures and processes required to get their work done at the bank and avail of its different products and services. Currently banks have their own web-sites, mobile applications and facilities like internet banking, mobile bank-ing but sometimes, these sources can be a bit overwhelming for most of the users who are either not well versed with technology or in some cases where the information is too scattered to search for easily.

There are different types of platforms provided by different banks but people are facing problems accessing them (different GUIs, too much navigation). Although Customer Care centers are available, there are lot of wait times and redirection in some cases, leaving the customer with no choice but to experience considerable delays getting a simple informational query resolved.

People have queries about various bank policies, loans, fixed deposits. This results in unnecessary crowd in banks for inquiry. Banks also face problems solving repeated queries of customers. This is time consuming and banking staff gets frustrated. Manpower and money gets wasted for separate inquiry counter.

Natural language processing Dogo Rangsang Research Journal UGC Care Group I Journal ISSN : 2347-7180 Vol-13, Issue-5, May 2023 Page | 156 Copyright @ 2023 Authors is actually an umbrella term that includes two related methods: Natural Language Understanding and Natural Language Generation. Natural language understanding (NLU) figures out the meaning behind text and speech. Think of this as reading or listening. This involves taking unstructured text and speech input from humans and converting it to structured formats that computers understand. When you ask Alexa for a weather report, for example, it uses natural language understanding to figure out what you're saying. Natural language generation (NLG) refers to computer-generated text and speech. NLG turns structured data into text and speech that

humans understand. Continuing our previous example, Alexa uses natural language generation when it responds 'It is sunny today. Would you like to place an order for sunglasses.

A chat bot is a conversational agent that interacts with users in a certain domain on certain topic with natural language Sentences. Normally a chat bot works by a user asking a question or initiating a new topic. Chat bots can be called as software agents that simulate an entity usually a human. These are the software with artificial intelligence which allows them to understand users input and provide meaningful response using predefined knowledge base.

Chat Bot for Banks: Developing a chat bot will provide a smart solution to solve these queries, provide information as and when required, improve service and increase number of customers. It removes human factors included in organization and can give 24/7 hours service to increase productivity.

We intend to provide a chat bot interface for customers which could be available on the web and on any hand-held devices. Customers can mention their queries in natural language and the chat bot can respond to them with correct answer. Proposed chat bot application is easily accessible to customer thereby solving redundant queries anywhere anytime. As there will be fast response for inquiry, this will be time saving for both bank and customers.

II LITERATURE REVIEW

S.H. Aparaj, C. Shashank, and R. Bhagat, "Smart Bot - A Virtual Help Desk Chat Bot," ICAICTE2013 (International Conference on Advanced Information Communication Technology in Engineering, 2013).

Abstract:

FAQs are mostly provided on the company's website to inform their service and product. It's just that the FAQ is usually less interactive and presents too much information that is less practical. Chatbot can be used as an alternative in providing FAQ. In this study, chatbots were developed for BTPN in providing information about their products, namely Jenius. Chatbot developed utilizes natural language processing so that the system can understand user queries in the form of natural language. The cosine similarity algorithm is used to find similarities between queries and patterns in the knowledge base. Patterns with the highest cosine values are considered to be most similar to user queries. It's just that, this algorithm does not pay attention to the structure of the sentence so that it adds checking the structure of the sentence with the parse tree to give weight to the pattern. This chatbot application has been tested by 10 users and it was found that the suitability of the answers with user input was 84%. Therefore the chatbot developed can be used by BTPN to provide Jenius product information to consumers more interactively and practically.

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Abstract

The stock market now includes smart banking as a fundamental component. In order to improve customer service, banks have developed certain policies, strategies, and objectives. Smart banking policy has become a very popular way to fulfill the demand and desires of the customer. The consumer of online banking will benefit from the reduction of needless time, effort, and financial loss. By establishing a continuous digital connection between bankers and customers, smart banking will simplify and streamline the customer's banking experience. Have all of your questions addressed by utilizing smart banking services from the convenience of your home or workplace. This policy will exclude additional wait times for lengthy lines for bank withdrawals and deposits of cash; in this instance, both the consumer and the bank will profit from the advantages of smart banking services, which are provided conveniently and meet all of the demands of the customers.

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The purpose of the project is to make any domain-specific website, in our case banking, more usable by integrating a chatbot that serves as an interface for customer inquiries about services. This reduces customer interaction time with websites, thereby valuing their time and improving their overall experience. As part of this project, we explored and attempted to create an intelligent chatbot that could extract relevant information, recognize various intents and execute the pre-mapped actions. To create a contextual assistant for the above purpose, we used the RASA framework. To train the model, we constructed a custom dataset that includes multiple intents and entities. Additionally, we provide some python scripts (RASA actions) that will be executed when some intents are detected. Our solution consisted of creating a pipeline having a chatbot and several actions triggered by the chatbot. These actions will connect with the database and then provide the required data or make changes according to the user's query and display the feedback back to the user via the chat widget.

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Abstract—Chat bots are intelligent systems that understand user's natural language queries and respond accordingly in a conversation, which is the focus of this study. It is more like a virtual assistant, people feel like they are talking with real person. They speak the same language we do, can answer questions. In banks, at customer care centers and enquiry desks, human is insufficient and usually takes long time to process the single request which results in wastage of time and also reduce quality of customer service. The primary goal of this chat bot is, customer can interact with mentioning their queries in plain English and the chat bot can resolve their queries with appropriate response in return. The proposed system would help replicate the customer service experience with one difference that the customer would be interacting with a bot instead of a real person and yet get the queries attended and resolved. It can extend daily life, by providing solutions to help desks, telephone answering systems, customer care centers. This paper explains the dataset that we have prepared from FAQs of banks websites, architecture and methodology used for developing such chat bot. Also this paper discusses the comparison of seven classification algorithms used for getting the class of input to chat bot.

III EXISTING SYSTEM:

the evolving landscape of banking, AI-powered chatbots have become integral to enhancing customer service and operational efficiency. e systems are designed to handle a variety of tasks, from answering frequently asked questions to assisting with complex financial transactions.

Examples of Existing Banking Chatbot Systems:

1. Erica by Bank of America: Ericas an AI-driven virtual assistant that helps customers with tasks such as checking balances, making payments, and providing spending insights. Since launch, Erica has garnered millions of users and handled millions of queries, significantly enhancing customer engagement. (superrpress.com)
2. Eno by Capital One: Eno monitors customers' accounts for unusual activity, assists with bill payments, offers personalized insights based on spending habits. Eno's proactive approach to customer service has been well-received by users, highlighting the potential of chaots to go beyond reactive support. (seriorpress.com)
3. Chatbot by Commonwealth Bank: Commonwealth Bank has integrated AI into its messaging services and lihat with customers, allowing for more sophisticated interactions and the ability to answea broader range ofuestions. This integration has led toignificant productivity boosts and enhanced customer service. (theaustralian.com.au)
4. LLM Suite by JPMorgaChase: JPMorgan seveloped an in-house generative AI product called LLM Suite, which assists employees with writing, idea generation, and

summarizing documents. This tool is part of the bank's broader strategy to integrate AI across its operations to improve efficiency and service delivery. ([reuters.com](https://www.reuters.com))
These examples illustrate how banks are leveraging AI-powered chatbots to improve customer interactions, streamline operations, and offer personalized financial services.

Disadvantage :

- Data Security Concerns
- Emotional Intelligence Limitations
- Accuracy and Reliability:
- Complex Financial Transactions

IV PROPOSED METHOD

ChatFin is an AI-driven platform designed to enhance financial operations by automating tasks such as data querying, reconciliation, flux analysis, variance analysis, and analytics. By leveraging natural language processing (NLP), ChatFin enables users to interact with financial data using simple chat commands, streamlining complex processes and improving efficiency.

Advantage:

- Seamless Integration
- Advanced AI Capabilities
- Cloud Flexibility
- Enhanced Security

V SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 This figure represents basic blocks of the whole system consisting of chatbot, website and database and how communication occurs between them.

V RESULTS AND SCREEN SHOTS

To run project install MYSQL and then install python 3.7 and then copy content from DB.txt file and paste in MYSQL console to create database.

Double click on run.bat file to start python web server and then will get below page

```
C:\Windows\system32\cmd.exe
E:\vittal\Feb24\BankChatbot>python manage.py runserver
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\pymysql\__init__.py
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\pymysql\__init__.py
Performing system checks...
(1764, 600)
System check identified no issues (0 silenced).
You have 15 unapplied migration(s). Your project may not work properly until you apply the migrations for app(s): admin,
auth, contenttypes, sessions.
Run 'python manage.py migrate' to apply them.
February 11, 2024 - 15:24:53
Django version 2.1.7, using settings 'Chatbot.settings'
Starting development server at http://127.0.0.1:8000/
Quit the server with CTRL-BREAK.
```

In above screen python server started and now open browser and then enter URL as <http://127.0.0.1:8000/index.html> and then press enter key to get below page

In above screen click on 'Admin Login Here' link to get below login page

In above screen admin is login and after login will get below page

In above screen click on 'Train ML Algorithms' link to train algorithms and get below page

Algorithm Name	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	FSCORE
KNN	95.73076881339745	96.89424136840449	91.03999099938004	93.96193282331466
Random Forest	99.15014164305948	97.73251898665839	96.92307692307692	97.299829942630428
SVM	96.88385269121812	98.02697967869408	90.32949562258074	93.67797084736893

In above screen can see result of all ML algorithms and in all algorithms Random Forest got high accuracy and now 'Logout' and sign up new user

New User Signup Screen

Username: kumar
 Password:
 Contact No: 9998887776
 Email ID: kumar@gmail.com
 Address: hyd
 [Submit]

In above screen user is entering sign up details and then press button to get below page

New User Signup Screen

Signup Process Completed. You can Login now

Username:
 Password:
 Contact No:
 Email ID:
 Address:

In above screen sign up task completed and now click on 'User Login' link to get below page

User Login Screen

Username: kumar
 Password:
 [Login]

In above screen user is login and after login will get below page

In above screen click on 'Interact with Chatbot' link to get below page

In above screen in text box I entered some text and then press button to get reply from Chatbot like below page

In above text area 'You' refers to user question and then can see Chatbot answer and similarly you can ask any question from dataset and get reply

In above screen I entered some questions and then Chatbot replied for all questions

VI CONCLUSION

The majority of banks provide internet banking for our convenience, and we profit from it at every step of the transaction process. For example, you can pay your bills, transfer money, and

examine a history of your checking account activities all from a web browser. Everything you do with your finances is a little bit easier when you can bank from the comfort of your couch. Banks only offer these services for our convenience. Your banking information is accessible on your computer or mobile device from any location where you have Internet connection. One of the numerous advantages of internet banking is its accessibility, but it also makes banking incredibly convenient. There is no longer any need to wait in a large line at the bank. Moreover, online banking offers a variety of options for various tasks, making money transfers and payments simpler. You can conduct transactions while on the go, whether you're in a traffic jam or at work. In order to prevent humiliation if your account doesn't have enough money to cover everything on your shopping list, it is now even simpler to check your balance before making cashless transactions. In addition to the aforementioned advantages, the majority of banks will provide a highly distinctive choice for internet banking customers in the form of cash withdrawal and cash deposit home delivery services. By establishing an ongoing digital relationship between the banker and the client for the purpose of providing bank service, related transaction activities will simplify and streamline the customer's banking experience. Use these banking services in the convenience of your home or workplace to get all of your questions addressed. This approach will eliminate additional wait times for lengthy lines to deposit and withdraw money from banks; in this scenario, both the client and the bank will profit from and have access to smart banking services. Generally, it is advised that bank management make sure that online banking technology is integrated into the company's operations. In order to stay competitive, create corporate growth, and increase consumer trust by taking a proactive rather than a reactive strategy, management must increasingly look for inventive methods to use it. Management should appoint a chief mobility officer to help systems of direct consumer contact succeed as a result of these gadgets' power transfer to individuals.

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